

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Transport for London

Identifying physical assets on
the London Underground

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1 Executive Summary

Transport for London (TfL) operates the largest metro network in Europe, covering 750km of track. Sheer size makes maintaining detailed records about assets on the network extremely difficult, which has implications for the ability of TfL to maintain asset conditions and plan for appropriate upgrades. If we can ascertain track asset information from data held by TfL, that could be incredibly valuable and allow the operator to better maintain and upgrade its track. Therefore, the main objective of this challenge is to achieve “identification (localisation and classification) of physical assets on the London Underground from image data”.

The provided data covers more than 100km of track, representing about around 20% of the London Underground network. The original collected dataset was in three-dimensional point cloud format, which was then converted to 2D image data by TfL. The original raw dataset comprised 5TB of data, which was reduced by a factor of four during the conversion process. Despite its large scale, only a small fraction (just 60 images, representing 0.0337% of the total data) was labelled, with the majority of the data remaining unlabelled.

This challenge involved a comprehensive exploratory analysis of data, training and testing of modified state-of-the-art U-Net [8] and Segment Anything [4, 7] models. With exhaustive experiments, this work achieved results of 100% recall and 91% precision along with high accuracy and F-Score metrics. Both qualitative results and quantitative metrics for each type of model and task are discussed in the report in detail. As a secondary task, this work also performed the computation of spacing between different railway track sleepers. Furthermore, we also presented the results of dimensionality reduction analysis and detection of vegetation encroachment during post-processing work. Lastly, we present some potential future directions and recommendations, which mainly include suggestions for reconstruction of 3D images, the use of ensemble models, type of sleeper classification, image filtering quality, and several other areas of improvement in data and modelling.

2 Introduction

Transport for London (TfL) is the key authority overseeing London's transportation infrastructure, including the extensive rail network that encompasses both the London Underground and Overground systems. With an annual budget of £60-80 million allocated for maintenance and renewal, TfL requires detailed and accurate information on current track assets. A depiction of some of these assets is shown in Figure 1. The main objectives of this project are to detect and classify the following assets on the rail track:

1. Ballast: Crushed stones or gravel placed under and around sleepers to provide stability, distribute load, and aid in drainage.
2. Sleeper: Horizontal support members placed perpendicular to the rails that maintain track gauge and transfer loads from the rails to the ballast.
3. Running Rail: The primary rail on which the train wheels run, providing a continuous surface for smooth movement.
4. Conductor Rail Ramp: A sloped section of the conductor rail that facilitates the train's pickup shoe to connect smoothly to the conductor rail.
5. Conductor Rail: A third rail that supplies electrical power to trains through a pickup shoe, typically used in electrified rail systems.
6. Points Machine: A device that operates switches (points) to change the direction of trains by moving rails at track junctions.
7. Tunnel Wall: The structural surface that forms the boundary of a railway tunnel, providing protection and support for the enclosed space.
8. Rail Clip: A fastening device used to secure rails to sleepers, ensuring they remain in position under dynamic train loads.
9. Vegetation: Plants, bushes, or grass near the railway tracks that need to be managed to ensure safe and unobstructed rail operations.
10. Others: Any additional elements related to railway infrastructure,

such as signalling systems, track beds, or fences, that contribute to safe and efficient rail operations.

Figure 1: Visualization of Features (Image Credit/Adapted by: Transport for London TfL)

This project utilises image data derived from point cloud data generated by track trolley scans to detect and classify various track features. In this procedure, we get track trolley capture data in the form of point clouds, which are then converted to image data (procedure described in below Section). Please note this capturing of point cloud data and then conversion to image data is already done by TfL. However, an investigation of different assets using this derived data is conducted in this report. In order to classify and detect such assets, this project followed multiple steps including: (1) analysing and pre-processing of data, (2) training of a U-Net [8] model, (3) training of a SAM [4, 7] model, (4) qualitative evaluation of 2D and 3D results, and finally, (5) presenting a quantitative analysis of both trained models.

Using these approaches, we achieved the goal of 100% recall and 91% precision in identifying the correct class of asset. These models

demonstrate excellent performance for the detection and classification of assets, which will support the effective management and maintenance of the rail network in future for Transport for London (TfL).

2.1 Background

TfL operates the largest inter-city rail network in Europe covering 750km of track. Its sheer size makes maintaining detailed records about assets on the network extremely difficult, which has implications for the ability of TfL to maintain asset conditions and plan for appropriate upgrades. Currently, when work or maintenance is planned, teams of surveyors are contracted to survey asset conditions - a costly process that can therefore only be done sparingly. One part of survey works is a laser scan of the track, which collects point cloud data that maps the space of the track and surrounding area. This data is used exclusively for track gauging (which is the width and height of the rails), however, it is incredibly rich and has depth information to 3mm of accuracy. TfL has point cloud data (part of which got converted to image data) for around half the network, if we can ascertain track asset information from it, that could be incredibly valuable and allow TfL to better maintain and upgrade its track.

TfL provided point cloud data (along with image-converted versions) from track trolley scans to investigate these features. The challenge will use a dataset collected by an Amberg trolley (shown in Figure 2) equipped with a spinning laser for Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR). An Amberg Survey refers to a system/methodology developed by Amberg Technologies, a Swiss company specializing in infrastructure measurement and surveying solutions, particularly for railways, tunnels, and other linear infrastructure. Amberg Surveys are laser scans of track which produce 3D representations of track space. The laser measures distances from a fixed point above the track centerline, creating a cylindrical point cloud. This raw point-cloud data was then converted into high-resolution depth maps, with a resolution of 1 cm by 0.005 radians. These depth maps, encoded as flat tables, provide detailed 3D representations of the track environment, allowing for easy identification of objects based on their surface shapes. It is important to note that an "Amberg Trolley" is equipment of TfL that TfL uses for data collection. They are used in many other areas of building/land surveying, but

Amberg makes a trolley that fits on a rail track. By definition, point clouds are datasets that represent objects or space. These points represent the (X, Y, Z) geometric coordinates of a single point on an underlying sampled surface. Point clouds are a means of collating a large number of single spatial measurements into a dataset that can then represent a whole. Point clouds are most commonly generated using 3D laser scanners and LiDAR (light detection and ranging) technology and techniques. Here, each point represents a single laser scan measurement. The data, collected and owned by Transport for London (TfL), represents approximately 560 km of track, covering about 75% of the network.

Figure 2: Amberg trolley for Data Collection

The approach followed to convert point-cloud data to image data includes cylindrical point-cloud data conversion into depth-maps. These depth-maps, encoded as flat tables, provide a 3D surface representation of the track environment, allowing for easy visual identification of track objects based on their surface shapes. This system collects distance measurements from a fixed point above the track centreline, converting cylindrical point-cloud data into depth-maps that encode the 3D surface of the track environment in flat tables. The image format is TiF images which are generated through point-cloud data. Firstly, point cloud data is unwrapped, then laser data for each point is flattened. Secondly, depth is

estimated by pixel image to represent 3D data. Lastly, two images get generated: one for reflectivity, and the other for depth map respectively for each tile of point cloud data. “*Reflectivity*” in point cloud laser data refers to the measure of a surface’s ability to return or reflect laser light, providing information about the material properties and intensity variations in the scanned environment.

This challenge utilises image data (provided by TfL) and aims to design a system capable of detecting and identifying assets automatically, ultimately helping TfL with further asset inspections. Another task focuses on extracting detailed information about sleeper assets, including identifying sleeper types and computing the distance between them. Accurate sleeper spacing is crucial for track stability and safety, as it ensures optimal load distribution to the ballast and subgrade. Proper spacing also helps prevent track misalignment, reduces maintenance, and improves overall railway performance.

2.2 DSG objectives

This Challenge focused on two main tasks “detection of features”, and “distance prediction among sleepers”. Details of both tasks are given below.

Task 1: Feature Detection

This is the primary task and will focus on detection of features in the point cloud images. The features will include installed sleeper and rail types, sleeper spacing, location of track side equipment (lubricators, point machines, signalling equipment), location of drainage systems, accurate positioning of features along the rail (expansion switches, joints, welds), conductor rail (3rd and 4th rail) type, position, and endpoints.

Task 2: Distance Prediction among Sleepers

The second task is to identify further details about the sleeper assets identified. This includes computation of the distance between sleepers by identifying shapes and different types of sleepers. Sleeper spacing computation is vital for ensuring the stability, safety, and durability of railway tracks, as it optimises load distribution from rails to the ballast and

subgrade. Proper spacing prevents track misalignment, reduces maintenance needs, and enhances overall performance.

The outcomes of these tasks will be both qualitative and quantitative metrics. With qualitative results, we mean image results that show detection of objects (in this case, objects are assets) using the proposed approaches. These results will show the boundaries of the assets (drawn around them) in the images. These boundaries will be the detection results of our approaches. Quantitative metrics will show the computed numbers for metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and f-score. These metrics are conventional metrics, which indicate how good models or approaches are in the detection/identification of objects. Nevertheless, these qualitative and quantitative results will clearly demonstrate how well our proposed approach is performing on TfL data and how much performance we achieved in both tasks.

3 Data overview

3.1 Dataset description

The data covers 560 km of track, representing about 75% of the London Underground network. The total volume of data is 5TB, which was reduced four times after conversion from point cloud data to images. The data is incomplete simply because there are areas which haven't been scanned yet for the purposes of gauging. The dataset in the form of images for this challenge, provided by Transport for London (TfL), consists of 1.2 TB of scanned images capturing rail infrastructure assets. The dataset focuses on nine key assets: running rail, ballast, sleepers, trackside vegetation, points machines, tunnel walls, conductor rails, rail clips, and conductor rail ramps. The image data covers over 100 km of track, representing approximately 20% of the London Underground network. Specific classes with their label indices are shown in Table 1.

Data Pre-processing Extensive pre-processing was carried out before making the data available for this challenge. The original dataset, captured in ZFS format, included detailed information such as the angle of capture, distance for each point, and reflectivity values. Pre-processing

Labels	Class labels
Background	0
Rail Clip	10
Running Rail	40
Sleeper	60
Ballast	80
Vegetation	100
Conductor Rail Ramp	120
Conductor Rail	140
Points Machine	160
Tunnel Wall	180
Other Classes	200

Table 1: Label colors with corresponding color codes.

involved error identification and exclusion, as well as data cleaning to ensure accuracy. A key step involved converting the point cloud data into TIFF images, where depth and reflectivity information were separated into two images, and paired together in a single TIFF file. For the labelled data, each TIFF file includes an additional masked image. Figures 3a, 3b, and 3c illustrate examples of a single TIFF file for labelled data. Each file consists of three layers: the first layer represents depth, the second layer displays reflectivity, and the third layer contains the masked image.

Data characteristics and scope The entire dataset is extremely rich in spatial information, enabling accurate measurement of key properties such as sleeper spacing and conductor rail positions. While most of the images were captured in 2014, the assets themselves are largely static, and we assume their condition has remained mostly unchanged.

The original raw dataset comprised 5 TB of data, which was reduced by a factor of four during the conversion process. Despite its large scale, only a small fraction—just 60 labelled images, representing 0.0337% of the total data has been labelled, with the majority of the data remaining unlabelled.

The dataset represents physical objects and errors such as light reflecting off shiny running rails were identified and excluded with high confidence

Figure 3: Example of TfL Image Data

during pre-processing by TfL. With these efforts, TfL ensured the team that the data used in the challenge was as clean and accurate as possible, especially in terms of identifying key infrastructure assets. Please note that extensive testing of quality of data is out of scope for this challenge.

3.2 Data quality

Data quality is assessed using suggestions provided by Mougan et. al. [6] while considering the following aspects of data quality:

- **Appropriateness:** The dataset is highly relevant to the challenge questions. It was specifically designed to address the key issues outlined in the challenge, providing targeted information about the rail infrastructure assets. This ensures that the data effectively supports the analysis and insights required to meet the challenge objectives.
- **Readiness:** The dataset is comprehensive, including ample data for

the assets in question, and is well-documented. The challenge owners provided additional metadata for asset labelling in the labelled data. Furthermore, the data owners were readily available to assist with any data-related questions or concerns throughout the project.

- **Reliability / Bias:** The dataset is of substantial size of 1.2 TB, and provides a good representation of most asset classes. However, certain labels, such as point machines and conductor rail ramps, are under-represented in the labelled data due to their infrequent occurrence on actual rail tracks. Additionally, some noise is present in the images, as they were captured through real-time scanning, a common source of expected variability. This noise was addressed later during the image pre-processing phase.
- **Sensitivity: Was the data private or confidential?:** The data is classified as sensitive and is internal to TfL. A breach could potentially jeopardise TfL's security and operational integrity. According to the Alan Turing Institute TRE (Trusted Research Environment) guidelines, the dataset is categorised as Tier 1 in terms of sensitivity, reflecting its high level of confidentiality and the need for stringent protection measures.
- **Sufficiency:** The labelled dataset is quite limited, consisting of just 60 images, which will be used for both training and testing the models. However, we have access to a vast amount of unlabelled data—1.2 TB—that can be leveraged for asset segmentation.

3.3 Exploratory data analysis

For exploratory data analysis, we employed a systematic approach which can be summarised as follows:

1. Analyse classes of assets with their indices. We refer to these indices as class labels.
2. Visualizing the contour shapes, by which we mean the boundary around the shape of object
3. Computing occurrence of each class

- Object/Instance-based Analysis
 - Pixel-based Analysis
4. Distribution of class counts per image
 5. Distribution of assets across test and train dataset
 6. Spatial and statistical properties analysis
 7. Other analyses

Our investigation with above steps are discussed in detail below.

3.3.1 Class labels

The TfL data owners provided the labels of classes that they used while creating the masks for the greyscale images. These indices range from 0 to 255. Specific values of each index explored in TfL data are shown in Table 1. Transport for London (TfL) provided coloured masks where each colour represents a different class; however, the mapping of colours to classes was not disclosed. Additionally, while greyscale images reflected numerical values corresponding to these colours, the specific values were also not provided.

3.3.2 Visualisation of contours

The next investigation is related to visualisation of contour shapes to get a sense of how the masks are positioned within each image. Figures 4a and 4b are examples of contour maps for rail tracks and sleepers in one of the images is shown below, illustrating the spatial layout of these components. These visualisations are important for understanding data and performing informed pre-processing and training of model. Currently, our analysis just verified the shape of rail tracks and sleepers and provided us with the visualisation of data.

3.3.3 Computing occurrence of each class

Next, we computed the total occurrence of each label class, including classes 0 and 255, where 0 represents the gaps between each mask boundary and 255 represents the background in the image.

(a) contour for rail track

(b) contour for sleeper on the rail track

Figure 4: Visualization of Contours for Sleeper and Rail Track.

Object/Instance-based analysis The bar graph in Figure 5 indicates that the label with the highest occurrence is *Sleeper* (class 80), followed by Tunnel Wall (class 180). The *Points Machine* (class 160) appears least frequently, which is expected since points machines are relatively rare along the tracks.

Figure 5: Bar graph counting the occurrence of each label

Pixel-based analysis Our analysis of the average number of pixels per class label is shown in Figure 6. These findings are important for understanding how many pixels are available for each class. If the number of pixels for a particular class is very low, it indicates that the class may not be well learned by machine learning models. Conversely, if a class has a higher number of pixels, the model is more likely to learn that class effectively. This analysis also provides insight into whether the dataset is balanced or imbalanced. The results from this investigation align closely with expectations: the central portion of the images primarily captures the tunnel walls due to the scanning method, which focuses on rail tracks and their surroundings. As a result, the Tunnel Walls class contains the highest number of pixels, followed by the Ballast class on the tracks, with the vegetation class appearing next in frequency.

Figure 6: Bar graph counting the pixel captured by each label

3.3.4 Distribution of class counts per image

We also explored the distribution of class counts per image in the datasets. Results of this investigation are shown in Figure 7. We can observe high variation in the number of assets for each class across the two datasets, with the rail clip, sleepers, and ballast classes exhibiting the highest level of variation. The medians for each class are similar across the two datasets. It is unclear what effect a reduction or increase of variation in assets per image for a particular class would have on model performance, as we

were not able to test this during the DSG. This can be a future area for exploration to further improve model performance.

Figure 7: Distribution of class counts per image for train and test datasets

3.3.5 Distribution of assets across test and train dataset

We also analysed the proportional distribution of assets across the test and train datasets. This analysis is important to communicate how many images (asset count) we got from TfL for each class (asset), as well as what percentage of them are present in the testing and training dataset. This analysis is presented in Figure 8. We found that the highest number of images are in sleeper and ballast. There are very few images for *conductor rail ramp*, *tunnel wall*, *points machine*, and a few others. In percentage distribution, we also observed an approximate 80/20 asset count distribution across the training-testing datasets for most of the classes, except for the *points machine* class, which had no representation.

Figure 8: Proportional distribution of asset classes across the test and train datasets

3.3.6 Spatial and statistical properties analysis

As part of our analysis, we also examined the spatial and statistical properties of various labelled objects by studying their depth and reflectivity across multiple images. We visualised the depth and reflectivity histograms side by side for each label class, providing a comparative view of how pixel intensities are distributed. Example of depth and reflectivity pixel distribution analysis for assets like Ballast, Vegetation on rail track, and Points machine is shown in Figure 9a, 9b, and 9c. This analysis gave us insights into the physical characteristics of each component. A distinctive trend observed across the labels was a concentration of pixels at the edges of the histograms, which we suspect might represent noise captured consistently in all the images.

(a) Depth and Reflectivity pixel distribution for Ballast

(b) Depth and Reflectivity pixel distribution for Vegetation on rail track

(c) Depth and Reflectivity pixel distribution for Points machine

Figure 9: Depth and Reflectivity pixel distribution

3.3.7 Other Analyses

We also conducted an image reflectivity analysis for reflectivity mask on training dataset. As discussed above, *reflectivity* in point cloud laser data refers to the measure of a surface's ability to return or reflect laser light, providing information about the material properties and intensity variations in the scanned environment. The correlation graph of this investigation is shown in Figure 10. A correlation graph for image data visually represents the relationship between pixel intensities or feature values across different channels, images, or regions, helping to identify patterns, dependencies, or similarities within or between image datasets. In this matrix, image similarity is calculated across all image pairs in the dataset. Figure 10 is an additional analysis which we conduct to show if there are any misalignments or discrepancies within data. However, we found it reasonable and couldn't do further analysis due to time limitations (discussed further in Section 4.3.4).

4 Approach

4.1 Research question

The primary research question posed in this challenge is as follows:

How can we identify (localise and classify) physical assets with sleeper spacing computation for the London Underground image data?

This research question can be divided into two parts:

1. Detection (Localisation and Classification) of physical assets
2. Computation of Spaces between Sleepers

4.2 Scientific approach

In addressing the challenge of detecting assets in underground railway networks, we adopted two distinct approaches by employing the U-Net [8] and Segment Anything Model (SAM [4, 7]) for image segmentation. U-Net, known for its excellent localisation and efficiency with limited data, served as our primary model, setting a solid foundation for precise asset

Figure 10: Image reflectivity analysis for reflectivity mask, training dataset

segmentation. To further enhance the model’s adaptability and robustness, we integrated SAM, celebrated for its state-of-the-art performance and ability to handle a diverse range of segmentation tasks. This dual-model strategy allowed us to effectively manage the varying and challenging conditions typical of underground environments, combining the strengths of both models to deliver a comprehensive and scalable solution for high-quality segmentation outcomes.

We divided our approach into three parts:

1. pre-processing of data
2. Segmentation of assets

3. Computation of spacing between sleepers

The methodology followed for each of these parts are detailed below.

4.3 Data pre-processing

4.3.1 De-noising

To improve the chances of the segmentation models [3] succeeding, the images can be de-noised to remove white pixels, which are where there is no data from the point cloud. By taking a nearest neighbour approach and inferring the values of white pixels from those around it, the white pixels can be filled in. This method works well for the type of noise seen in the raw 2D reflectivity and depth images, where single pixels are missing data randomly. An example of the de-noising can be seen in Figure 11. It can be very easily visible that white dots (noise) in Figure 11 (a) have disappeared in Figure 11 (b), which demonstrates the good performance of applied method. However, quantitative analysis of de-noising can be done for such results in future to further support the conclusion of high performance.

4.3.2 Splitting image

One approach to simplifying the images before training in the semantic segmentation models (e.g. U-NET [8], SAM [4, 7], CNN [5]) is to split the image in the middle and join the two edges that were originally on the outside left and right of the image in the centre. This makes the tracks move to the centre of the image from the outside. Figure 12a shows an unsplit image, and Figure 12b shows a split and rejoined image. It is worth mentioning that the centre of the image mostly covered the tunnel area initially, which was not useful for TfL asset detection. However, after transformation, the centre area consists of assets which need to be detected by models and are useful for TfL.

Unfortunately, due to the labelling being done with the tracks at the edges, there are often gaps at the edge of the mask layer. When the mask layer is cut and rejoined, the gaps at the edges are moved to the centre and form a discontinuous mask at the centre. An example of this can be seen in Figure 13. To fix this problem, the original raw image data could be made

(a) Noisy Image

(b) De-noised Data

Figure 11: Difference between raw and de-noised images.

with the track in the centre since it is the most important feature before human labelling.

4.3.3 Image augmentation via centre segment removal

Another effective data pre-processing technique we employed for augmenting the existing labelled dataset involves removing the middle section of each image and stitching the left and right parts together. This approach enables us to generate additional images from the original labelled data without compromising the integrity of the visual information. By shifting the outer sections inward, we preserve key spatial features

(a) Original reflectivity image of the railway track

(b) Reflectivity image after middle-stitch transformation, shifting the outer sections inward

Figure 12: pre-processing on Reflectivity of Railway Track

while increasing the diversity of the dataset.

This method proves especially useful for models like U-NET, SAM, and CNN, as it ensures that essential elements (e.g. railway tracks, sleepers) remain intact. Simultaneously, it eliminates less relevant content, such as tunnel walls or sky, that often occupy the centre and contribute little to segmentation tasks. Moreover, this strategy helps balance the dataset by offering varied perspectives of the same scene, ultimately enhancing the model's ability to generalise.

Figure 14 provides an example of a chopped image (reflectivity), which corresponds to the same image in Figure 3. It demonstrates how the left and right portions containing critical information—such as railway tracks, ballasts, sleepers, and vegetation—are merged after removing the centre section.

4.3.4 Image similarity

We also explored exploiting image similarity as a pre-processing approach, such that comparable image variability could be maintained across the testing and training datasets.

We initially attempted a rough pixel-by-pixel comparison approach. This involved calculating an average pixel value for the depth layer and the reflectivity layers of each image. We then calculated an

Figure 13: Example of mask that has been split and rejoined in the centre.

Figure 14: Reflectivity layer of a chopped image

average-of-averages across all dataset images and calculated the variation in average pixel values across images in the dataset. However, we ultimately discarded this approach, since the effect of reflectivity and depth artifacts on average pixel value was significant.

As an alternative, an ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF) algorithm was implemented to detect and match keypoints between images. Image similarity was then assessed according to the number of matching keypoints across the images. The results were robust and allowed sorting of images from most similar to least similar. Figure 10 shows the similarity

analysis of the reflectivity layers in the training dataset. In this matrix, image similarity is calculated across all image pairs in the dataset.

Due to time and technical constraints, we were not able to explore whether this approach of image pre-processing could be leveraged to improve model performance. We recommend exploring this approach in the future if model performance is to be improved.

4.4 Detection of assets using image segmentation

To effectively address the challenge of asset detection in an underground railway network, our team has adopted two distinct methodologies utilising advanced image segmentation techniques. The initial approach employs a Fully Convolutional Network (FCN), specifically the U-Net architecture [8], which is renowned for its proficiency in various applications across multiple domains. The second approach leverages the cutting-edge capabilities of the SAM (Segment Anything Model [4, 7]), which represents the forefront of developments in image segmentation technology.

In implementing the U-Net architecture, we developed a tailored version of the neural network specifically designed to meet the unique requirements of our project. This customisation involved structural modifications to the network to enhance its suitability for the specific characteristics of the asset detection task in an underground environment. Furthermore, by incorporating the SAM (Segment Anything Model), we aim to achieve a more robust solution that can extract additional information from the images, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of our asset detection capabilities.

4.4.1 Method 1: U-Net

Our approach to utilising the U-Net model is aimed at establishing a reliable baseline for our project. Recognized for its robust performance across various applications, U-Net promises to not only serve as a solid foundation but also potentially meet the specific asset detection needs within the underground railway network. This strategic application allows us to compare our results with a proven standard and explore the adaptability of U-Net to fulfil our project goals effectively.

One challenge in implementing U-Net was adapting it to handle our unique image format, which includes layers for depth, reflectivity, and mask, rather than the standard RGB input. This required modifications to the initial layers of the neural network to process this different type of input effectively.

The adoption of a U-Net architecture trained on multi-layer TIFF images significantly enhances the accuracy, efficiency, and thoroughness of rail track asset detection and classification for Transport for London. This method offers a substantial improvement over traditional manual inspection techniques and conventional computer vision methods.

To test our approach, we developed a U-Net model architecture from scratch. The training process involves several critical steps: preparing the TIFF images, pre-processing the data, configuring the U-Net architecture, and training the model. Instead of resizing large images, which can lead to a significant loss of detail, we opt for splitting them into smaller tiles or patches. This method preserves the intricate details necessary for effective segmentation, allowing us to process each patch separately and then seamlessly integrate the results post-inference.

pre-processing for U-Net In our data preparation process, the depth and reflectivity layers are stacked along the channel dimension to create a 2-channel input image for the model. Normalisation is applied to the input images by dividing each pixel by the maximum pixel value, scaling the pixel values to a range between 0 and 1. This is a standard pre-processing step for neural networks to optimise data for processing. Additionally, both the input images and masks are segmented into smaller patches, using a default size of 512x512 pixels with an overlap of 128 pixels. This overlap ensures that the boundaries between patches are smoothly handled during both training and prediction phases, facilitating effective boundary management in the model's output.

U-Net model architecture

1. **Input Layer:** The model is designed to process images formatted as 512x512 pixel patches, each containing two distinct data channels.
2. **Encoder Path (Downsampling):**

- **First Block:** The initial stage involves a 2D convolutional layer with 32 filters of size 3x3, followed by batch normalisation and Leaky ReLU activation. This setup is repeated with another similar convolutional layer, concluding with a 2x2 max pooling to reduce spatial dimensions and a dropout step to prevent overfitting.
 - **Second Block:** This block uses 64 filters, enhancing the model's capability to capture more complex patterns while reducing spatial resolution.
3. **Deeper Layers and Decoder Path (Upsampling):** The decoder uses upsampling techniques to increase the feature maps' dimensions, including:
- **Upsampling/Transpose Convolution:** To enlarge the spatial dimensions of the feature maps.
 - **Concatenation and Convolution:** Outputs are concatenated with corresponding feature maps from the encoder to preserve high-resolution details, followed by two convolutional layers similar to the encoder.
4. **Activation and Loss:**
- The Leaky ReLU activation function is used to avoid the "dying ReLU" problem. Dropout is applied in certain layers to reduce overfitting. The model employs the Adam optimiser and Categorical Cross-entropy loss function, ideal for multi-class segmentation, where each pixel's class label is precisely predicted.
5. **Intended Output:** The model is configured to classify each pixel into one of 12 classes, suitable for complex segmentation tasks involving multiple categories.

U-Net model training We have employed smaller patches to train the U-Net model. This approach has significant advantages as it allows for handling more manageable image sizes while preserving most of the original image's resolution. This method facilitates efficient processing

Figure 15: U-Net Architecture [9]

and training on standard hardware without compromising on the detail required for accurate image segmentation.

Hyperparameter settings The values of hyperparameters that we found suitable in our experiments are listed as follows:

- **Optimiser:** Adam
- **Loss Function:** Categorical Cross-entropy
- **Learning Rate:** 1e-4 (0.0001)
- **Batch Size:** 4
- **Epochs:** 50

However, incorporation of automated Hyperparameter Tuning is recommended for future for getting further enhancement in performance.

Architectural Details An architecture of U-Net model is shown in Figure 15.

Furthermore, we used following architectural parameters:

- **Input Shape:** (512, 512, 2)

- **Classes:** 12 classes
- **Activation Function:** Softmax

4.4.2 Method 2: Segment Anything Model (SAM) implementation

We use the Segment Anything Model (SAM) 2 because of its versatility and state-of-the-art performance in image segmentation tasks. SAM's ability to adapt to a variety of inputs and its robust segmentation capabilities make it an excellent choice for complex environments such as underground railway networks, where diverse and sometimes ambiguous objects must be accurately identified and classified. This model enhances our project's effectiveness by providing high-quality, detailed segmentations that improve over more traditional segmentation methods.

SAM 2 is a successor of the SAM model developed by Meta in 2023. SAM 2 builds upon the strengths of its predecessor by advancing foundational models that were originally designed for Natural Language Processing (NLP). By applying contrastive learning techniques, SAM 2 can map image data and text, allowing it to generalise to new visual concepts and unfamiliar data distributions through prompt engineering. For our task, we have 1.2TB of unlabelled data, which positions SAM 2 as a promising model for training on large data batches. This could result in a highly robust, state-of-the-art model capable of studying and segmenting rail tracks in both 2D and 3D spaces.

However, since we have very limited labelled data, there is a risk that the model could be under-trained and may overfit when performing inference on the unlabelled data. Consequently, it may not be the optimal choice at this early stage. However, we have experimented with SAM 2 to evaluate its ability to detect the classes in our mask for a smaller subset of test data and to see whether it can outperform the U-Net model during initial tests. A notable challenge is that SAM 2 traditionally does not accept a 3-channel input, necessitating the conversion of our data to a 2-channel input, excluding the depth information. To achieve this, we converted the file format to PNG without losing spatial information (meaning 2D image space is not compressed). This ensures that the model can still effectively

learn different asset classes without compromising the quality of the input data.

To experiment with the SAM 2 model, we downloaded the pre-trained weights and model setup from Facebook Research. Since our data is unconventional and lacks sufficient labelled samples for comprehensive training, we opted for a zero-shot learning approach combined with a batch processing loop, processing one image at a time. Given the complexity of our dataset, where multiple asset classes exist within a single mask, we aimed to improve the generalisability of the model. This method improved segmentation accuracy by 30%, offering a rough yet effective mapping.

In addition to the architectural setup, we implemented a custom loss function and a backpropagation loop for instance-based learning. One of the main challenges was managing the input size: our images are 734×5120 , while SAM is trained on 1024×1024 dimensions. This discrepancy led to significant challenges in maintaining performance.

Image processing approach: To address this, we introduced an image pre-processing step using tiling and stitching techniques. We tiled both the images and masks into 1024×1024 segments and, after processing, stitched them back together. This allowed us to preserve spatial fidelity while resizing the processed images and masks to 734×734 . By using this approach, we maintain the integrity of the pixels during batch processing, ensuring that no detail was lost. In addition to this approach, we also experimented with padding the input images to resize them to 5120×5120 . However, this method caused a global reduction in image size, making it difficult to accurately interpret pixel-level details across the entire padded image.

SAM architecture This model consists of the following components:

1. **Input Layer:** The SAM 2 model processes images as 1024×1024 pixel patches, with three data channels corresponding to RGB visual inputs. This design captures high-resolution spatial

information, making it suitable for segmenting complex visual scenes across diverse environments.

2. **Encoder Path (Downsampling):**

- **First Block:** The model begins with a 2D convolutional layer featuring 64 filters of size 3×3 , followed by batch normalization and GELU activation. Another convolutional layer is applied, and the block ends with 2×2 max pooling for downsampling. Dropout is used to prevent overfitting.
- **Second Block:** The second stage uses 128 filters to deepen the feature extraction capability, with another downsampling operation to reduce spatial dimensions and capture finer image details.

3. **Vision Transformer (ViT):** A key feature of SAM 2 is the integration of a Vision Transformer (ViT) [2] after the initial downsampling blocks. The ViT divides the image into smaller patches and applies self-attention mechanisms to each patch, allowing the model to understand global context and relationships within the image. This enhances the model's ability to capture both fine and large-scale features.

4. **Prompt Encoder:** SAM 2 includes a prompt encoder that uses contrastive learning to map both image data and textual prompts. This feature enables SAM to generalise to new visual concepts through prompt engineering, making it highly adaptable to unseen objects or categories in segmentation tasks. The prompt encoder accepts inputs such as bounding boxes, points, or textual prompts, making it versatile across a wide range of segmentation applications.

5. **Decoder Path (Upsampling):**

- **Upsampling Layers:** The decoder path uses transposed convolutions to upscale the feature maps back to the original resolution (1024×1024).
- **Concatenation and Convolution:** The upsampled feature maps are concatenated with corresponding encoder features to retain detailed information at every stage. This is followed by

convolutional layers similar to those in the encoder, further refining the outputs for precise segmentation.

6. **Output Layer and Loss:** The final output layer uses a Softmax activation function to assign each pixel to one of several classes. SAM 2 utilizes the Adam optimizer for gradient descent and Categorical Cross-entropy as the loss function, which is ideal for multi-class segmentation tasks.

SAM training: The SAM 2 model employs a distinctive training approach where it generates a centroid for the object of interest (the segmented object) and uses this point as a reference for inferring class labels across multiple segments, as seen in Figure 16. This method is particularly effective when handling two or more input classes, allowing the model to learn associations between different segments. This flexibility enables SAM to deliver reasonably accurate segmentations even with limited labelled data, making it well-suited for complex environments like underground rail networks.

Furthermore, to enable smarter inference in a complex model, we categorised the labels as sub-labels within the mask. Since each class contains multiple labels, this hierarchical structure simplifies the model's task of predicting and inferring associations between different segments. By organising labels in this way, the model can make more accurate predictions and efficiently handle complex segmentation scenarios.

Hyperparameter settings The values of hyperparameters that we found suitable in our experiments are listed as follows:

- **Optimiser:** Adam
- **Loss Function:** Categorical Cross-entropy
- **Learning Rate:** $1e-4$ (0.0001)
- **Batch Size:** 1
- **Epochs:** 1000

However, incorporation of automated hyperparameter tuning is recommended in the future for further enhancement in performance.

Figure 16: Centroid for each class of labels

Architectural details Furthermore, we used the following architectural parameters:

- **Input Shape:** (1024, 1024, 3)
- **Classes:** Customizable, often 12+ for complex segmentation tasks
- **Activation Function:** Softmax

4.5 Sleeper spacing

The second task is to identify sleeper features, including spacing between sleepers. Code was developed to calculate the sleeper spacing from a mask image. This masked image can be the ground truth labelled dataset or the output of the U-Net or SAM models.

The middle stitch transformation was used to calculate the sleeper spacing. This combines the left and right rails so that the entire sleeper position can be reconstructed. As previously discussed, there can be a gap in the mask at the centre. This does not affect the sleeper spacing calculation significantly, as the mean position was calculated from multiple points on each sleeper. The SciPy multidimensional image processing library was used to locate objects in the array labelled as the sleeper class.

Figure 17: Example of a mask from the labelled dataset. Sleeper centre positions (red points) are identified for sleeper objects determined using an image. An example of multiple sleeper objects belonging to the same sleeper component is outlined in yellow. Examples of small sleeper objects which have been removed from the analysis are outlined in magenta.

Multiple sleeper objects are identified for each sleeper due to the intersection of other components, see Figure 17. The centre and area of each sleeper object were calculated based on the number of pixels in the object. In some masks, there were small sleeper objects detected, see Figure 17 for an example. The position of the small sleeper objects are not representative of the position of the whole sleeper. Figure 18 shows the distribution of sleeper object areas. This shows that there are clear outliers below 100 pixels. Therefore, all sleeper objects with an area below 100 pixels were removed from the analysis. It is assumed that the training dataset distribution is representative of the whole dataset.

The midline of each sleeper was determined by fitting a linear line through all points on the sleeper. The left and right extent of the sleepers were also identified. From this, the Euclidean distance between sleepers was calculated at the left and right edges of the sleeper and at the centre.

5 Results and discussions

We divided this section into four main parts: First, we present results using U-Net-based models in Section 5.1.1. Secondly, we elaborate results using the SAM-based approach in Section 5.1.2. Third, we

Figure 18: Distribution of sleeper object area from the training dataset.

discuss results for sleeper spacing computation in Section 5.2. Lastly, we discuss post-processing methods (in Section 5.3), including noise reduction and vegetation encroachment near railways. At the end of this section, we also discuss limitations of our approach with possible directions.

5.1 Image segmentation results

5.1.1 Method-1: U-Net-based approach

An example of qualitative results for segmentation of assets is shown in Figure 19 and 20. Segmentation of different assets can be seen with different colours. We evaluated the model on the testing data on multiple metrics, including accuracy, intersection over union, precision, Recall, and F1-score. Results for the detection task using U-Net trained model are shown in Table 2.

It can be seen in Figure 20 that model prediction matches with ground truth masks, and difference mask also indicates how close ground-truth and prediction masks are. Class distribution is also attached to these prediction masks to indicate which number of pixels associated with each class. This

Figure 19: Image segmentation using the U-Net model

Metrics	Accuracy	Mean IOU	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Performance	90%	37%	88%	90%	89%

Table 2: Performance (Pixel-based) for Task-1 using Method 1: U-Net based Approach

distribution shows that an image does not contain pixels from only one class but includes multiple classes with a reasonable number of pixels each. As shown in Figure 19 and 20, there's a band at the bottom of the segmented image. This is due to the challenge of reconstructing the image after splitting them in tiles with size 512x512. However, the evaluation metrics demonstrated good performance even on the small-sized dataset provided by TfL.

Furthermore, we tested results on object level and we got a recall of 100% and precision of 91%. These results (shown in Table 3) suggests that the U-Net model trained is capable of finding the objects that were labelled, but sometimes it labels images with objects that are not present in the ground truth image. It is important to note that here with "object-level" we refer to "asset-based", and 100% recall indicates our model is able to find all originally labelled assets in images. In other words, by object-level, we mean class-level, which refers to the computation of precision and recall for detecting each class (which represents an asset in TfL). These results can also be verified from Figure 21, where the model was able to detect

Figure 20: Comparison of ground truth values and predicted

all 21 and 6 classes.

The initial hypothesis was tested: U-Net performs well for this task because we are working with specialised multi-layer TIFF images (depth, reflectivity, mask) rather than standard RGB images. As we had a relatively small labelled dataset for training and we required a lighter-weight model that can run on less powerful hardware, U-Net seems to be a model that has the potential to label images faster than

Metrics	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-Score
Performance	100%	91%	100%	95.23%

Table 3: Performance (Object-based) for Task-1 using Method 1: U-Net based Approach

```

OLD_GPU, USE_FLASH_ATTN, MATH_KERNEL_ON = get_sdpa_settings()
Number of distinct classes in the segmentation map: 21
Classes found: [ 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 9 10 12 18 19 21 33 36 40 42 46 48 63 67]
Number of distinct classes in the original mask: 6
Classes found: [ 0 10 40 60 80 120]

```

Figure 21: Example of Class Prediction Results for Image using Method-1(U-Net model) for Task-1

other complex methods.

5.1.2 Method-2: SAM-based approach

The initial hypothesis adopted for this work is that SAM 2, being a complex neural architecture, requires a significant amount of data to perform at an optimal level. The model’s structure is highly sophisticated, and its ability to generalise depends on substantial input data to fully capture the nuances of various classes and objects within an image. For our task, while we have a large dataset from Transport for London, SAM 2 is more suited for long-term use and large-scale datasets rather than the immediate segmentation tasks in this project.

The segmentation results show that SAM 2 correctly predicted 6 out of the 8 main classes in the original mask of an image. While this is a reasonable performance, it did not achieve the level of precision and predictability that we observed with UNet. The model’s predictions were somewhat inconsistent, with some class labels being misclassified, particularly in complex areas of the image. Please note this study is conducted on all test images but shown only for one image in the report. Our analysis suggests that while SAM 2 has potential for future use, its immediate effectiveness is limited by the relatively small amount of labelled data available.

In summary, while SAM 2 shows promise for broader applications, as

Figure 22: Predicted Segmentation mask from SAM 2 on Unlabelled Dataset

shown in Figure 22 (which displays an example of a test image and its segmentation mask). Different objects are segmented by different colours. For large-scale datasets, it may not be the best fit for the current task, where high accuracy is required with limited training data. This reinforces the need for a simpler, more established architecture like UNet for immediate tasks, while SAM 2 could be developed further for future use with larger annotated datasets of TfL.

Additionally, the model's performance metrics reveal signs of overfitting. With an Intersection over Union (IoU) score of **0.6** (i.e. 60%) and a loss value hovering around **0.8** (i.e. 80%), it is evident that while the model is achieving moderate accuracy on the training data, it struggles to generalise effectively. The high loss suggests that the model is memorizing the training data rather than learning meaningful patterns, further indicating over-fitting. This confirms that SAM 2, though powerful, may not be the best choice for our current task with limited labelled data, and reinforces the need for a more balanced approach to prevent over-fitting.

5.2 Sleeper spacing computation results

5.2.1 Ground truth from labelled dataset

The methodology for calculating sleeper spacing seems to be working on the majority of masks in the labelled training set. However, quantitative

analysis of sleeper spacing was not part of the aim and could be part of future work. An example of this is shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Sleeper locations calculated from the labelled mask image. Red crosses indicate the leftmost edge, centre and rightmost edge of the sleeper. Sleeper spacing was calculated between these points.

However, the methodology fails for some images where there are additional rails in the image. An example is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Example of where the sleeper distance calculation has poor performance.

Figure 25 shows the distribution in sleeper spacing calculated from all training images. The outliers, such as Figure 24, are excluded manually from this analysis for clarity.

Figure 25: Distribution of calculated sleeper spacing from the training dataset. Outliers are removed for clarity.

5.2.2 U-net predicted mask

The sleeper spacing calculation was carried out on the predicted mask for five images in the test dataset. The U-net prediction was carried out on the original images. Therefore, the mask has the rails on the left and right of the mask. The middle stitch transformation was applied to the predicted mask before the calculation of sleeper spacing.

For some sleepers, the spacing calculation agrees well with the ground truth calculated spacing. Figure 26 shows an example where the methodology works well. However, for some sleepers, the methodology fails due to regions in the image which are predicted to be sleepers incorrectly. Figure 27 shows an example. The predicted and ground truth sleeper distances are shown for all sleepers in all five images in Figure 28. For many points, there is good agreement, however, there are also significant outliers. Improvements to the method could be made to minimise the impact of false-positive sleeper regions predicted by the U-net model. Further improvements to the U-net model would also improve the agreement. Despite these outliers, this has shown that the sleeper spacing has the potential to be predicted using a U-net model.

5.3 Results after post-processing

In this work, due to limited time, we mainly focused on pre-processing of data, training and testing of models. However, we also performed two different directions of analysis as post-processing, details of our investigations are presented in this section.

5.3.1 Methodology for identifying vegetation encroachment near railways

At this step, the vegetation that is close to the railway and needs to be trimmed was identified. To address the research question, an analysis was conducted using data from depth maps obtained from Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) measurements. The depth maps provide information about the proximity of detected objects to the railway. In these maps, darker colour tones correspond to objects closer to the rail, with lower pixel values in the depth layer indicating shorter distances. As shown in the Figure 29 and 30, almost all of the components of railways have similar distributions of depth. It is only vegetation with a wider distribution of depth, meaning that some vegetation parts are closer and some parts are further from the railway components.

A threshold needed to be established to determine the depth at which vegetation should be removed. This threshold was set based on an analysis of the depth distribution of the ballast and sleeper classes, which represent the track bed and components closest to the railway. The ballast layer was specifically chosen as a benchmark for determining the threshold, as it provides a more conservative and safety-oriented reference point. The assumption is that any vegetation detected closer to the railway than the ballast may interfere with the smooth operation of the train and thus require trimming.

To identify the appropriate threshold, the depth distribution of both ballast and sleeper layers was analysed. The upper fence of the ballast depth values, calculated using the interquartile range (IQR) method, was selected as the threshold. Using the upper fence of the ballast ensures that the selected threshold errs on the side of safety, accounting for potential variations in the depth of railway infrastructure components. Vegetation with depth values lower than this threshold—meaning

Figure 29: The distribution of depth for assets: sleepers and ballast.

Figure 30: The distribution of depth for assets: railway components.

vegetation detected closer to the railway than the upper fence of the ballast—was flagged for removal. This approach ensures that vegetation that may interfere with railway operations is identified and can be managed proactively. In Figure 31, there are 9 plots showing the labels of the masks. They include all the files in the dataset that have vegetation labels. Among these 9 files, there are two of them (plotted on the top) where the vegetation is closer than the threshold to the railway components. The threshold is shown by the dashed red lines in these two plots.

Figure 31: 9 TIFF files having vegetation.

5.3.2 Principal component analysis for dimensionality reduction

We are assuming that to investigate different characteristics of classes (assets), we can construct clusters for different classes using principal component analysis (PCA [1]).

PCA [1] is a dimensionality reduction technique often used in clustering to simplify data by projecting it into a lower-dimensional space while preserving as much variance as possible. By reducing the number of features, PCA helps improve the performance of clustering algorithms, like K-Means, by eliminating noise and redundant information, making

patterns or clusters in the data more distinct. Although PCA itself does not perform clustering, it transforms complex datasets into a format where clustering becomes easier and more effective, especially in high-dimensional data. Our analysis of different assets using PCA is shown in Figure 32. This analysis is an additional investigation of data for post-processing. We observed that most of the assets (*conductor rail*, *sleeper*, *point machine*, *rail clip* and many more) fall in the nearby space in the graph, except *tunnel wall* in the PCA graph. This also confirms that tunnel walls are very different from assets, and TfL also confirm we can ignore them in the detection as they are not the actual asset.

Figure 32: PCA plot of principal component 1 and principal component 2

Furthermore, Figure 33 shows the explained variance of the principal components in the PCA. The explained variance in the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a measure of how much of the total variance in the data is captured by each principal component. The explained variance is used to determine the number of principal components to retain, by taking those that collectively account for a high

percentage of the total variance. This helps in identifying the most significant patterns and simplifying the dataset without losing substantial information. In this case, it takes 4 principal components to account for 90 % of the variance in the data (while it takes a total of 5 to reach 100%), meaning that we cannot reduce the number of variables.

Figure 33: Explained variance of the original variables in the PCA plot.

6 Discussion and limitations

One significant limitation that we encountered was the lack of sufficient computational power to run our models effectively. This issue forced us to employ various strategies, such as cropping images, using smaller batch sizes, and adjusting our neural network architectures to function with only 16 GB of GPU memory. These constraints not only slowed our execution but also limited our ability to experiment with different solutions. Additionally, we experienced a complete lack of access to the GPU on the

afternoon of Wednesday, resulting in an abrupt pause in our development activities on the third day.

Another major challenge was the limited number and quality of our labelled images. We had only a small dataset of 53 images, all manually labelled, which presented inconsistencies, especially around the edges of the images. These inconsistencies typically manifest as incorrect gaps around the sleepers that do not actually exist. Although we reviewed these labels, the inaccuracies might still affect the reliability of our models, as our ground truth may not accurately represent real conditions.

The data images were captured using a LIDAR scanner, which was operated by a person walking with the device. This introduces the possibility of distortion in the scans. For instance, if the person pauses while walking, the LIDAR continues scanning in place, leading to compressed or “squeeze” sections of the image. Conversely, when passing through tunnels or making turns, the images may become stretched, particularly on the side of the turn. This results in one corner appearing more elongated compared to the other, as the LIDAR covers more distance on the outside of the curve.

7 Conclusion

The image data set was preprocessed to remove noise and find an optimal split using similarity scoring, and quality was determined. Two segmentation models (U-Net and SAM 2) were trained using the provided dataset and were able to segment the test set of images to a reasonable degree of accuracy. The predicted masks could then be post-processed to find the individual components in the mask. Quantitative values of area, height, width, average depth, and average reflectivity of each component could be extracted and then used to further analyse the dataset to identify sleeper distances, vegetation proximity to the track, and identify subclasses via clustering in principal component analysis.

8 Future work and recommendations

We were in the process of developing a design that processes a depth map and a 2D mask to generate a 3D mask. This is achieved by first converting the depth image into a 3D point cloud and then mapping the pixels from the 2D mask to the 3D space as shown in Figure 34a. The idea is that once we have a robust segmentation model capable of producing highly accurate masks, these masks can be fed into this program to create detailed 3D masks across the entire unlabelled dataset. This will enable us to extend the 2D segmentation results into a 3D domain, making it possible to perform more advanced spatial analysis as shown in Figure 34b. Completion of this design and evaluations is one of the important directions for future work.

Figure 34: Re-Construction of 3D and Segmentation.

One of the key benefits of this approach is the ability to calculate the approximate volume of small objects in various asset classes, such as rail clips, sleepers, and conductor rails. By calculating the volume of these segmented objects, we can classify them by size and shape, which opens up possibilities for multiple applications. For instance, we could use this data to identify faults like deformations, cracks in the rail, or accumulated debris, which are often critical for maintenance. These volumetric measurements could also help with tasks such as estimating material wear, erosion, or displacement, all of which are important for infrastructure monitoring.

Furthermore, the 3D point cloud data allows us to perform texture analysis, which adds another dimension to the object identification process. By analysing the surface texture of the objects in the 3D point cloud, we can detect surface irregularities that may indicate potential faults or defects. For example, the texture of a rail clip may show unevenness or wear, or the ballast may display irregular textures due to foreign objects or erosion. Texture analysis can also help differentiate between different materials or surface types, which could be valuable for identifying anomalies like surface rust, cracks, or corrosion.

The combination of 3D point cloud data and texture analysis would enable more accurate and detailed classification of objects within the asset classes. With this approach, we can move beyond simple segmentation to offer a comprehensive system that not only identifies objects but also assesses their condition, making it suitable for tasks like fault detection and predictive maintenance. This approach would also significantly enhance our ability to maintain safety standards and prolong the lifecycle of railway assets.

Further ideas and opportunities for future work are listed as follows:

- Ensemble learning can be suggested as a method to provide improved segmentation results by leveraging the complementary strengths of U-Net and SAM.
- Labelling work and performance of SAM2 model can be potentially simultaneously improved by utilising the current UNet implementation to automatically generate labelled class masks for database images. This will help more efficiently grow the dataset, which will help improve the performance of the SAM2 model, which requires a high volume of training data to perform well.
- Image filtering for quality control: Implement automated algorithms to balance and correct stretched or squeezed sections of images, enhancing the dataset's overall consistency for model training
- Apply our post-processing methods to predicted mask
- Sleeper type classification may be possible by making use of depth information of the top surface of the sleepers: Concrete sleepers tend to be concave, whilst wooden sleepers are flat. Alternatively,

measuring the endpoint heights with respect to the middle point height could be a fast methodology to assess sleeper type (shown in Figure 35a and Figure 35b).

- The relative heights of the centre and sides of the sleeper may be used to classify these types.

(a) Concrete sleeper

(b) Wooden sleeper

Figure 35: Sleeper Types: Concrete and Wooden.

9 Team members

Alphabetical order by last name

Laura Ballisat is a PhD student at the University of Bristol working on Monte Carlo simulation of DNA damage due to radiotherapy. She contributed to this project on the exploratory data analysis of the predicted segmentation mask.

Garima Chaudhary is a Data Scientist at Santander UK with over 4 years of experience in the banking and healthcare sectors. Her expertise spans data engineering, predictive modelling, and image classification. In this project, she contributed by conducting statistical data analysis for the image data and handling data pre-processing tasks.

Devjyoti Das is a Computer Vision researcher in the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering at the University of Strathclyde with a strong expertise in Deep Learning and Vision Models. He contributed to this project through data pre-processing, statistical data visualisation, SAM2 model implementation and output analysis.

Fatimah Faraji is a PhD student at the University of Essex. She is working on cybersecurity, Systemic risk management in critical infrastructure. She contributed to this project by data analysis, pre-processing, image analysis via contours and more simple approaches to segmentation.

Dr Francisco Gomez Medina is a Research Application Manager in Data-Centric Engineering at The Alan Turing Institute. His expertise includes Digital Twin implementation in high-value asset industries, data-centric engineering, and technology management. He contributed to this project through statistical data analysis, data pre-processing, model exploration, and output analysis.

Ben Jenkins is an EngD student at the University of Birmingham working on an industrial research project. His expertise include DEM simulations of granular materials, regression based predictive modelling, image analysis and processing as well as exploratory data analysis. He contributed to this project via image pre-processing, image analysis via contours and more simple approaches to segmentation and on the exploratory data analysis of the final predicted segmentation.

Dr Assemgul Kozhabek is a Research Associate in Data Science at Ulster University within the School of Computing, Engineering, and Intelligent Systems. During the course of this Data Study Group, she was nearing the completion of her PhD in Computer Science at Bournemouth University (Computing Department), which she has since successfully completed. Her research interests include complex networks, industry-specific data science, and transportation planning. Her primary contribution to this project is in data analysis, with a particular focus on data pre-processing.

Zahra Mahabadi is a PhD student at University College London. Her expertise is in spatial-temporal data analysis, travel behaviour modelling, and urban studies. She contributed to this project by data analysis and pre-processing and post-processing tasks.

Tiago Tamagusko is an AI-integrated Transportation Specialist with nearly a decade of experience developing and researching solutions for Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) and smart cities. He is a researcher at University College Dublin, focusing on transforming urban spaces into inclusive, green, and future-proof environments. His expertise includes

machine learning algorithms, computer vision, and their potential impact on the future of transportation. In this project, he contributed as a Facilitator, leveraging his transportation and computer vision expertise. He also developed a base code framework to test various image segmentation algorithms and conduct experiments.

Jenny Vega is a Software Engineer at Isomorphic Labs. She works building a platform that helps ML scientists to train their models and run inference at scale. She has experience fine-tuning and pre-training large models using supercomputers on cloud. In this project, she contributed by developing the U-Net model..

9.1 Principal Investigator

Dr Asra Aslam is a Research Fellow at University of Leeds, Visiting Researcher at Newcastle University, and General Chair for Women in Computer Vision. She is Machine Learning Lead on multiple NIHR Funded medical science projects, teach AI/ML in Health Sciences Department, and supervisor of 7 PhD/master's students. Her research interests are Computer Vision, Deep Neural Networks, Smart Cities, and Health Sciences. As a PI, Asra formulated the research problem while collaborating with TfL, identified sub-tasks, gave directions, helped in computer vision methods & codes, and finalising this report.

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